

Table 4. Secondary data information, 2022. See Table 3 for details.

ID	Species	ST	T (°F)	T (° C)	Camera	Notes
s2523ul	Photuris lucicrescens; frontalis	20:22			Max	
s2524ur	Photuris forresti	20:34	75	24	Max	Rainstorm/thunder and lightning
s2524ul	Photuris lucicrescens; frontalis	20:23			Max	
s2528ul	Photuris lucicrescens; frontalis	20:26			Max	
s2529ul	Photuris lucicrescens; frontalis	20:26			Max	
s2601ur	Photuris forresti	20:40			Max	Possibly Photinus consimilis as well
s2607ia	Photinus acuminatus	20:42	74	23	Max	Specimen ID by Luiz Da Silveira
s2607ic	Photinus carolinus	20:56	77	25	Max	Clear, calm
s2609ic	Photinus carolinus	20:57	73	23	Max	Clear, calm
s2609io	Photinus obscurellus	20:21	67	19	Fusion	possibly some Photuris mimicry (3-4 snappy bursts); clear
s2614ya	Pyractomena angulata	20:23	72	22	Fusion	clear
s2615xx	unknown	20:33			Max	
s2616ux	Photuris sp.	20:24	66	19	Fusion	possibly Photinus aquilonius too; fully overcast and windy
s2616xx	unknown	20:33			Max	
s2617xx	unknown	20:33			Max	
s2617bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:30	83	28	Max	calm, mostly cloudy
s2618bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:30	73	23	Max	calm, partly cloudy, RH: 62.5%
s2618xx	unknown	20:33			Max	
s2619bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:30	85	29	Max	wind 5mph, partly cloudy, RH: 25.7%
s2620bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:30	83	28	Max	partly cloudy, RH: 28%
s2620xx	unknown	20:34			Max	edge of farm field; chilly
s2621bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:31	66	19	Max	wind 2.5mph, RH 78%, rain 0.15in
s2621ug	Photinus greeni	20:26	65	18	Fusion	65F at 9pm, partly cloudy but nice
s2621xx	unknown	20:34	64	18	Max	raining; cameras on a slope
s2622xx	unknown	20:34			Max	access road with pond nearby
s2623bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:31	81	27	Max	wind 1.5mph, cloudy, RH:34%
s2623ug	Photinus greeni	20:26	62	17	Fusion	62F at 9pm, partly cloudy but nice
s2624xx	unknown	20:35			Max	woods between river and ridge
s2624bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:31	79	26	Max	cloudy, wind 1.4mph, stormy, rained earlier, RH: 38.4%
s2625bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:31	83	28	Max	cloudy, wind 1.4mph, hot and sticky, RH: 30%
s2625xx	unknown	20:35			Max	farm field, edge of mowed/unmowed areas; creek nearby
s2626bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:31	78	26	Max	cloudy, no wind, RH: 42%
s2626ic	Photinus carolinus	20:55	68	20	Max	Rain
s2627mx	mixed species	20:55			Max	Photinus pyralis, carolinus; Photuris versicolor complex
s2627xx	unknown	20:34			Max	tall grass, temperatures in mid 60s F
s2627bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:31			Max	
s2628mx	Photinus pyralis; Photuris sp.	20:44	73	23	Max	Photinus australis possible as well
s2628bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:31	83	28	Max	partly cloudy, no wind, RH:38%
s2629bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:31	76	24	Max	cloudy, wind 0.8mph, RH:58%, sprinkling
s2630mx	mixed species	20:54			Max	Photinus pyralis, carolinus; Photuris versicolor complex
s2630bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:31	78	26	Max	no wind, cloudy, RH:53%, sprinkling
s2630xx	unknown	20:35			Max	temperature upper 60s F, deep vegetation
s2701xx	unknown	20:35			Max	mowed path between farm field and tree line; creek behind
s2702xx	unknown	20:35			Max	raining, thunderstorm; mid 60s F; vegetation 6ft high
s2705xx	unknown	20:34			Max	raining on/off, humid, upper 60s F, in the woods
s2705ub	Photuris bethaniensis	20:28	72	22	Max	after rain, still some lightning but calm, 80%cc
s2706mx	mixed species	20:53	70	21	Max	Photinus pyralis, carolinus; Photuris versicolor complex
s2706ub	Photuris bethaniensis	20:27			Max	Warm, partly cloudy. Low firefly density
s2707xx	unknown	20:33	61	16	Max	small field, edge of mowed/unmowed area
s2708ip	Photinus pyralis	20:52	69	21	Max	high clouds
s2708xx	unknown	20:42			Max	former farmland; switchgrass, indian grass, wildflower mix
s2709xx	unknown	20:41			Max	meadow/no-mow lawn; surrounded by native trees (seeding is 2 yo)
s2710ip	Photinus pyralis	20:52	60	16	Max	clear
s2711ip	Photinus pyralis	20:51	72	22	Max	clear
s2713mx	Photinus pyralis; Photuris sp.	20:39	72	22	Max	
s2715bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:28	79	26	Max	RH: 57.5, different flash pattern as in July
s2716bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:28	85	29	Max	cloudy, wind 2mph
s2718bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:27	88	31	Max	thin clouds, wind 2.8mph, RH: 35.3%
s2720bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:26	90	32	Max	cloudy, wind 2.6mph, RH: 31.3%
s2724bw	Bicellonycha wickershamorum	19:24	70	21	Max	partly cloudy, calm, RH:90.8%
s2801ub	Photuris bethaniensis	20:10	75	24	Max	Wind S 5mph, 80%cc
s2803ub	Photuris bethaniensis	20:09	78	26	Max	Wind S <5mph, clear
s2809ik	Photinus knulli	19:13			Max	